

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase

.....

Two training workshops for VRE use and technical follow-up & upgrading

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
LL	Living Lab
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RI	Research Infrastructure
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This document supports **Deliverable D6.4 Two training workshops for VRE (Virtual Research Environment) use and technical follow-up & upgrading** as part of Task T6.1. *Virtual Research Environment and Blockchain demonstrator for data provenance, traceability & chain of custody, network identification support and Agro-Ecosystems Services valorisation & accountability.*

In recent decades, there has been a noticeable shift in the patterns of innovation and collaboration, indicating that science and innovation are becoming increasingly global, networked, and multipolar (Royal Society, 2011). As a result, research-supporting environments have become more prevalent and accessible, enabling users located anywhere to seamlessly access data, software, and processing resources managed by diverse systems in separate domains through their web browsers. These environments are commonly referred to as **Virtual Research Environments (VRE)** and are among the objectives of e-Infrastructures. Nowadays, a wide range of platforms are available that cater to these needs, as stated by Calyam *et al.* (2021). VRE can range from ad-hoc platforms that offer minimal access services to data stored in external repositories to complex management systems with advanced services defined over a wide range of resources.

A VRE can be defined as a platform in the form of a webspace designed to make it easier for users to find and securely access data and use it in innovative ways. A VRE provides seamless access to all services a data-user needs to do data-related work and collaborate with the community to create new knowledge (Candela *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, a VRE makes working with data more manageable and enhances communication among users (such as end users, decision-makers, and citizens).

Utilising a VRE enables individuals to store, locate, access, visualise, analyse, and collaborate on their data, thus minimising obstacles to joint projects. As a result, a VRE can be utilised to address scientific and managerial queries, such as those pertaining to agroecology. Within a VRE, users have the ability to communicate their actions, pinpoint them on a map, and interact with other users who share similar interests. Additionally, users can scrutinise the shared data to enhance their comprehension of specific processes or perform simulations to evaluate the impact of various scenarios (e.g., climate change or management decisions) on their activities. To ensure data security and traceability, these functions are executed within a safeguarded environment utilising cutting-edge tools (Ávila-Castuera, *et al.* 2022).

During ALL-Ready, an Agroecology VRE has been produced. This VRE is based on the architecture of the Tesseract VRE produced by LifeWath ERIC as a consequence of 10 years of ITIL-DevOps continuous improvement processes as a result of taking benefit of outstanding projects deliverables, among others: Creative-B, ENVRI+, COOPEUS & COOP+, GLOBIS-B, EGI.eu LifeWatch Competence Centre, etc. During the co-design process, it was agreed that, during the first stages of this potential Virtual Research Environment for Agroecology, a Virtual Lab would be designed to exchange and visualise information between Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Moreover, the use of the term Virtual Lab will be better understood by the end-users. Therefore, it was decided to use the term **Agroecology (AE) Virtual Lab** (see "A VRE for Agroecology" in Section 2 of Ávila-Castuera, et al., 2022 for more details).

The design of the AE Virtual lab was based on a participatory approach. The co-design process included forming a group of end-users based on the representatives of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures of the Pilot Network developed in the project ALL-Ready (Varga and Fehér, 2022). This group, called KeyUserGroup, participated in specific workshops, training and questionnaires that contributed to identifying and prioritising the functionalities and the validation and testing of the different releases of the platform (see section 2. Upgrade of the VRE).

The co-designed AE Virtual Lab has been defined as a collaborative platform, supported with Artificial Intelligence and Blockchain tools, to improve the collaboration, networking and knowledge sharing among members of AE Living Labs, Research Infrastructures and other Open Innovation Arrangements to foster the transition towards agroecology in Europe. By providing users with the tools and resources they need to connect and collaborate, the platform can help advance the field of agroecology and promote sustainable and equitable food systems. The prioritised functionalities are:

- **Visualisation of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures Maps:** The platform allows for the visualisation of maps that showcase the location and information about agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. This feature provides users with a better understanding of these institutions' institutional profiles and geographic distribution.
- **Visualisation of Agroecology Best Practices:** The platform includes a marketplace where users can create and view opportunities related to agroecology best practices. This feature allows users to share their experiences and learn from others, promoting the exchange of knowledge and improving agroecological practices.
- **Networking:** The platform offers several networking tools, including user profiles, messages, and the marketplace. These tools facilitate communication and collaboration among users, allowing them to connect with others who share similar interests or work on related projects.
- **Knowledge sharing:** The platform includes a repository tool that allows users to upload and share files related to agroecology living labs and research

infrastructures. This feature promotes disseminating information and knowledge among users, supporting collaboration and the development of best practices.

During the second phase of the project, and based on the updated risk identification and a development plan, WP6 continued the work on T6.1. by realising an operational version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab in two steps: in November 2022 (M25) and March 2023 (M29). After each release, training and validation sessions with the Pilot Network were organised in November 2022 (M25) and March 2023 (M29).

This report is the continuation of the D6.3 VRE & Blockchain ("LifeBlock" & Artificial Intelligence-based) demonstrator, based on the input of the Pilot Network Members during the co-design and validation process. It includes a description of the operational version of the AE Virtual Lab. Moreover, this deliverable includes the reports of the two training workshops for VRE use and technical follow-up & upgrading, aimed at building capacity and skills in the use of the VRE among the ALL-Ready project's Communities of Practice.

2. Upgrade of the AE Virtual Lab

2.1 Procedure for the upgrade of the Agroecology Virtual Lab

Developing a new release for the AE Virtual Lab is a collaborative process that involves careful planning and implementation, teamwork, and a focus on meeting user needs and requirements.

For the release of the new version of the AE Virtual Lab, a KeyUserGroup was launched among the members of the Pilot Network of AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. This KeyUserGroup was central to the validation of the incremental versions of the tool. We are focused on researchers, although we tried to involve other groups such as policymakers, the innovation sector (including farmers, cooperatives, companies, etc.) and citizens during the process

LifeWatch ERIC provided help to the members of the KeyUserGroup by:

- supporting creating a profile, add opportunities, search,
- helping them familiarise with the platform,
- answering all the technical and process questions,
- supporting at any level during the testing period,
- gathering feedback and answer questions,
- showcasing new functionalities.

The KeyUserGroup were contacted at least once per month or two months based on the advancements of the requirements identification and the development of the new functionalities. Online meetings, workshops, training and questionnaires were used to co-design and validate the requirements.

Once the preliminary requirements were collected, the design and validation phase started, following an agile methodology. Mockups and prototypes of the new features and changes were created and tested with the KeyUserGroup. This helped us better understand how the new release will look and function and allowed us to identify any potential issues early on.

With the design specifications in place, we started developing the new release. This stage involved coding and implementing the new features and changes. Once the new developments were completed, we extensively tested the new releases to ensure that they functioned as expected and met the requirements, including automated and manual testing.

After deployment, we closely monitored the new release to identify any issues or bugs that may have been missed during testing. We also gathered feedback from users and analysed performance metrics.

Finally, we continued to maintain and update the new release as needed. This includes fixing bugs, adding new features, and making any necessary changes based on user feedback.

During this process, two trainings were organised.

- November 2022. This workshop aimed to train participants on the pre-operational version of the AE Virtual Lab and validate mockups and preliminary functionalities of the platform.
- March 2023. The objectives of this workshop were to provide attendees with the necessary skills and knowledge to use the AE Virtual Lab. The workshop aimed to teach attendees all the different functions of the platform related to collaboration, networking and knowledge sharing, but also obtain feedback and inputs from the end-users to improve the tool.

2.2 Description of the upgraded version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab

2.2.1 Login Page

The AE Virtual Lab is accessible in the following URL: <https://agroecology.lifewatch.eu>

Figure 1. Login Page

The login page (Figure 1) presents two input fields (1) (email and password) in order to carry out the identification of the user by means of credentials.

It offers the possibility of signing as a user through (2):

1. LifeWatch ERIC
2. ORCID
3. Google
4. EGI

Additionally, registering can be carried out through the internal portal form (3). See Figure 2.

Figure 2 Registering new user. Internal form

Once the username and password have been entered and accepted by any of the channels above (using "Log in" button) (4), the portal dashboard will be accessed.

2.2.2 Dashboard

Once the username and password have been entered and accepted by any of the aforementioned channels, the application dashboard will be accessed (Figure 3).

The screenshot displays the LifeWatch ERIC dashboard landing page. At the top, a navigation bar includes 'Dashboard', 'Marketplace', 'Messages', 'Citizens', 'Innovation Sector', 'Policy Makers', 'Researchers', and 'Ecosystems'. The user is logged in as 'Hi, Daniel!' with a 'Sign out' option.

Key features are annotated with numbers:

- (1) Greeting: 'Hello, Daniel!'
- (2) Left sidebar menu: 'Map', 'Graph', 'Matches', 'Collabs', 'Network', 'Radar', 'Opportunities', 'Resources', 'News', 'Data'.
- (3) Main content area: 'Tips for Collaboration & Innovation' section, including 'COLLABORATION' tips, 'Community Events', 'Collaboration Status', and 'New Messages'.
- (4) Action buttons: 'Add Opportunity +', 'Invite Collaborator +'.
- (5) Bottom footer: Logos for SUMHAL, SmartFood, LifeWatch ERIC, ENIG [Lab], and EUROPEAN UNION.

Figure 3 Landing Page Dashboard

The home page will be divided into four basic zones:

- Top menu, divided into submenus (1):
 - Marketplace
 - Messages
 - Citizens
 - Innovation sector
 - Policy makers
 - Researchers
 - Ecosystems
 - Hi, Name (Profile)
 - Notifications (bell icon)
 - Sign out

- Leftside, divided into submenus (2):
 - Map
 - Graph
 - Matches
 - Collabs
 - Network
 - Radar
 - Opportunities
 - Resources
 - News
 - Data

- Central menu, where we can find a series of useful information that will be offered at first sight to the user (3):
 - Tips for collaboration
 - Community events
 - Collaboration status
 - New messages
 - New members and opportunities
 - New resources

It will also offer the possibility of adding one opportunity to invite a collaborator through two shortcuts by clicking two action buttons (4).

- Bottom menu, which will offer the possibility to change the presentation language of the portal, as well as links to contact information, helpdesk, and information about Disclaimers & Agreements (5).

2.2.3 Profile

By clicking on the *Hi, name* in the upper right corner, the user can access to the Profile section (Figure 4). The Profile showed the public information that will be shared with other users. By clicking on Edit Profile, the user can modify the user profile, add new information or delete the profile. The section is divided into:

- Profile (1)
- Attachments (2)
- Additional Information (3)
- Affiliation and Ecosystems (4)
- Activities (5)
- Opportunities (6)

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Profile' page in the LifeWatch ERIC system. The page is divided into several sections. The top section is a header with the user's name 'Hi, Daniel' and a 'Sign out' button. Below this is the 'Edit Profile' section, which includes a greeting 'Hello Daniel!', a profile picture placeholder, and buttons for 'View Profile' and 'Save Profile'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains fields for 'First Name' (Daniel), 'last_name' (Caro), 'Position' (Agroecology Services Integrator Assistant), and 'Organization' (LifeWatch ERIC). The right column contains fields for 'Research Sector' (Environmental Services), 'Ecosystem' (Agroecology), 'City' (Seville), and 'Country' (Spain). Below these are fields for 'Link to Website' and 'Areas of Interest', which includes tags for Agroecology, Biotechnology, Environmental Biotechnology, Innovation, Climate Change, Biodiversity, Living Labs, Green Cities, BigData, and Artificial Intelligence. At the bottom, there is a 'Description of your Activity' field with a rich text editor and a short bio.

(1) Edit Profile

First Name (visible) Daniel

last_name (visible) Caro

Position (visible) Agroecology Services Integrator Assistant

Organization (visible) LifeWatch ERIC

Research Sector (visible) Environmental Services

Ecosystem (visible) Agroecology

City (visible) Seville

Country (visible) Spain

Link to Website (visible)

Areas of Interest (visible)

Agroecology × Biotechnology × Environmental Biotechnology × Innovation × Climate Change × Biodiversity × Living Labs × Green Cities × BigData × Artificial Intelligence × Agriculture ×

Write some tag and press enter

Description of your Activity (short bio) (visible)

Normal B I U

provide scientific and technical support to the LifeWatch ERIC facilities on Agroecology topics in the related projects and the links with socio-economic analysis, international cooperation, knowledge management, building a Community-of-Practice of users, clustering with other relevant initiatives, organizing training services, sustainability plans, development of Virtual Research Environments and e-Services addressed to the main stakeholders

(2) Attachments

You can upload documents to be shown on your profile here. Feel free to upload your CV.

Drag 'n' drop some files here, or click to select files

(3) Additional Information

Email <input type="text" value="daniel.caro@fewatch.eu"/>	Nationality <input type="text" value="Spain"/>
Phone Number <input type="text"/>	Gender <input type="text" value="Male"/>
Birthdate <input type="text" value="dd/mm/yyyy"/>	Level of Education <input type="text" value="Doctoral Or Equivalent Level"/>
Address <input type="text"/>	Postal Code <input type="text"/>

(4) Choose your Affiliation and Ecosystems

Living Lab Affiliation <small>(visible)</small> <input type="text"/>	Research Infrastructure <small>(visible)</small> <input type="text"/>
Open Innovation Group <input type="text"/>	Choose your Research Areas
	☒ Environmental engineering ☒ Environmental biotechnology ☒ Other engineering and technology sciences ☒ Agriculture ☒ Forestry ☒ and fisheries ☒ Agricultural biotechnology ☒ Biological sciences ☐ Earth and related environmental sciences <input type="text"/> Select

(5) Activities

Desired Rate Per Hour (€)

Choose the activities you are interested in collaborating:

☒ Application of ICT tools for knowledge sharing among farmers	☒ Best agroecological practices identifications at farm scale	☒ Board member
☒ Brainstorming	☒ Case study	☒ Coaching
☐ Communication system	☐ Computing system	☐ Conference call
☒ Consulting	☒ Feasibility study	☒ ICT tools for improving decision-making process
☒ Innovation project	☐ Internship	☐ Laboratory/laboratory equipment
☒ Modelling	☒ Partnership	☒ Presentation
☒ Research consortium	☒ Research project	☒ Resilience/adaptability/vulnerability assessment
☒ Scientific data analysis and storage	☒ Socioeconomic and environmental impact assessment	☐ Speaker
☒ Strategy check	☐ Student thesis	☒ Systemic agroecosystem experiment
☒ Technology transfer	☒ Testing products	☒ Trial/research site
☒ Valorisation of agroecosystem services at different scales	☒ Whitepaper	☒ Workshop

(6) Add Opportunities

To complete your profile further, please add opportunities to the marketplace.

Figure 4 User Profile

2.2.4 Marketplace

A marketplace of the AE Virtual Lab is a section of the platform where users can discover and post collaboration opportunities in agroecology (Figure 5). This section is designed to facilitate the exchange of expertise, knowledge and resources between users of AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, as well as to foster collaboration and innovation in the field.

Figure 5 Marketplace

The Marketplace section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box, as well as four drop-down menus to filter the results and a "Add Opportunity" button that leads to a new form where user can enter new opportunities (1)
- Central menu: the search results will present the Opportunities that fit the search and filtering criteria as a table (2). Each opportunity will be displayed in a box, showing the nature of the opportunity (whether it is a service, an internship, a research project, etc.), as well as whether it is an offer or a demand, and the person who has introduced it. Likewise, the date of its publication and a brief summary of it will be reflected, with the possibility of expanding the information by clicking on the "View details" button. There the user can ask for collaboration or send a Message to the member who has published the Opportunity.

You can add Opportunities in this section by clicking the "Add Opportunity" button. This action will open a new form (Figure 6):

The screenshot shows a web interface for adding an opportunity to a marketplace. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links to Dashboard, Marketplace, Messages, Citizens, Innovation Sector, Policy Makers, Researchers, and Ecosystems. The user is logged in as 'Hi, Daniel' and can click 'Sign out'. The main heading is 'Add Opportunity to Marketplace'. On the left, a sidebar menu lists various features: Map, Graph, Matches, Collabs, Network, Radar, Opportunities, Resources, News, and Data. The main form area contains two radio buttons: 'Offering' (selected) and 'Looking For'. Below these are input fields for 'Opportunity Name' and 'Due Date' (with a date picker icon). There is a 'Category' dropdown menu and a 'Keywords' text field with a placeholder 'Write some tag and press enter'. A horizontal line separates the form into two sections. The first section has a 'Looking For/ Offering' input field. The second section is for the 'Description', featuring a rich text editor with options for Normal, Bold (B), Italic (I), Underline (U), Link, and Unlink.

Figure 6 Add Opportunities

2.2.5 Messages

The Messages section (Figure 7) of the AE Virtual Lab serves as a hub for online communication between users. It allows users to send direct messages to each other, attach files, create channels and teams, and search through previous messages and files. The messages section is designed to streamline communication between users, making it easier for them to collaborate and share information. By attaching files to messages, users can quickly and easily share documents and other resources with their collaborators, and by creating channels and teams, they can group conversations around specific topics or projects. Additionally, the ability to search through previous messages and files allows users to quickly find relevant information without having to scroll through a long conversation thread.

Figure 7 Messages Section

The Messages section is a tool designed to increase the power of informal conversations to increase creativity, innovation and collaboration among the members will be divided into three zones:

- Left menu (1): which will consist of a list of channels. Users can create private "Team" channels for teams and add working groups inside the "Team" via private channels.
- Central menu (2): where the chats will be displayed. Additionally, in the upper right corner you can find a series of links for group or channel information, notification preferences, attachments, and other useful information.
- Lower menu (3): text entry field.

2.2.6 Citizens, Innovation Sector, Policy Makers and Researchers

This section works as Directory of the main user types of the platform. You can search other users from here based on specific Keywords, Ecosystem or Location. You can access to their Profile, Send a Message or ask for collaboration.

Figure 8 Citizens Section

All directories are divided into two zones.

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box, as well as three drop-down menus to filter the results. (1)
- Central menu: the search results will present the Citizens that fit the search and filtering criteria as a table list (2). Each citizen will be displayed in a box, showing the name of the citizen, as well as the company or entity to which it belongs and the position it holds. Additionally, you can expand the information on each result by clicking on the "View Profile" button, send a message by clicking on the "Send message" button, or request a collaboration through the "Collaborate" button.

2.2.7 Ecosystems

This section includes the information on the Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Coordinators of the initiatives can Edit the information by completing information about the organisation. Moreover, the Ecosystem will appear in the section Map once the address is included.

Figure 9 Ecosystems

The Ecosystems section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box with two filtering drop menus. (1)
- Central menu: the search results will present as a table list, with relevant ecosystems that fit the search and filtering criteria (2), along with information on the nature of the Ecosystem, as well as its location (country) and a brief summary of its activity. Additionally, more information about each resource can be accessed by clicking on the "View Details" button.

The section for a specific Ecosystem is divided into:

- General Information I (1)
- General Information II (2)
- Certifications and Stakeholders involved (3)
- Specific domains of interest, production sectors and socio-economic aspects considered in the LLs or RIs (4)
- Opportunities offered and being looking for members of the Ecosystem (5)
- Members (6)
- Resources attached to the Ecosystem

Ecosystem
Edit

- Map
- Graph
- Matches
- Collabs
- Network
- Radar
- Opportunities
- Resources
- News
- Data

ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab

Living Lab

ÖMKi on-farm living lab is an agroecology-focused nationwide participatory experimentation network that includes variety of field trials and technology tests co-designed and co-implemented with farmers with the aim to improve and/or develop new organic/agroecological practices, products and technologies.

agroecology agriculture organic farming

[Chat Channel](#) [Website](#)

Address
Mikkóss tér 1, Budapest 1033, Hungary

Country:
Hungary

Research Areas:
Agricultural sciences,
Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries,
Other agricultural sciences

Industry Sector:
Farming

Certifications
ENOLL

Stakeholders involved

- Researchers
- Advisors
- Farmers
- Processors
- SMEs
- Academics
- NGOs
- Consumers
- Regional public bodies/authorities

Specific Domain of Interest

- Soil fertility
- Climate change adaptation
- Water retention
- Short supply chain
- Animal welfare
- Integrated pest management
- Climate change mitigation

Production Sectors

- Arable farming
- Horticulture (vegetable ornamental fruit)
- Animal husbandry
- Mixed farming

Socio-economic Aspects

- increasing farmers income and building better livelihoods for agroecology stakeholders
- developing and advising on innovative transdisciplinary agri policy
- increasing youth involvement/empowerment in agroecology
- building sustainable local food supply chains and markets

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

Opportunities We Offer

2023-03-18

Digital competences training

Service | Consorcio Fernando de los Ríos, GRANADA, Spain

View Details

2023-06-30

Field visit

Research project | ÖMKI, Budapest, Hungary

View Details

Opportunities We are Looking for

2023-03-18

Good practices about collaboration in agro-ecological food systems

Inspirational practice | ILVO-LLAEBIO, Merelbeke, Belgium

View Details

2023-06-17

AE LL incubator program manager

Service | ÖMKI, Budapest, Hungary

View Details

Members

Areas of Interest: agroecology, ict, research infrastructures, European Research Projects, e-Science

View Profile

Send Message

Researcher, ÖMKI

Areas of Interest: Agroecology, Agriculture, Agricultural policy

View Profile

Send Message

Resources

Research with the participation of Hungarian farmers

Agroecology

The ÖMKI on-farm research network is a system of innovative experiments carried out on Hungarian organic farms. It was established in 2012 and since then, the number of participants has been increasing continuously. This is the first research network in Hungary that is based on the active participation of farmers: the topics of our simple experiments carried out under realistic conditions are determined together with the farmers.

ÖMKI On-Farm LL youtube channel

View All Resources

2.2.8 Map

An essential feature of the AE Virtual Lab is a map that displays the locations of the AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures of the Network (Figure 10). This map can provide users with a visual representation of the global Network of agroecology

initiatives, and can help users identify potential collaborators and partners in different regions. A search tool is also included (1).

When a user clicks on a location marker on the map (2), they are taken to a specific section of the platform that provides more information about the corresponding living lab or research infrastructure. This section may include a description of the research focus or goals of the initiative, information about the team members or partners involved, and details about ongoing projects or collaborations. By providing users with easy access to this information, the platform can help facilitate connections and collaborations between different living labs and research infrastructures, and can help advance the field of agroecology more broadly.

Figure 10 Map Section

2.2.9 Graph

A tool for identifying existing crucial "online" network components was created as one of the components of the AE Virtual Lab (Figure 11). A database of agroecology papers and projects was designed and developed by LifeWatch ERIC to put up this component. Following this, the required software was produced to download AE papers and projects from various sources and upload them to the database. An academic artificial intelligence platform based on the gathered data was created after the data was unified and the database's data was debugged. In the left side of the graph, you can find some buttons to change the type of graph (1).

Figure 11 Graph Section

2.2.10 Matches

This section displays potential collaborations based on keywords and descriptions that match the user's profile and interests (Figure 12). Users can review the matches and contact other users to initiate new collaborations.

The Matches section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu will consist of a search box and three drop-down menus to filter the results among the suggested Opportunities and Members (1).
- Central menu: the automated suggestion (2) of Opportunities from the Marketplace and Members, including names and surnames, sector, position, company or entity, location and areas of interest. Three buttons will be provided to see each person's entire profile, send a message, and request a collaboration.

Figure 12 Matches Section

2.2.11 Collabs

This section displays ongoing collaborations that users are involved in. Users can view the progress of their collaborations, communicate with other collaborators, and access important documents and resources related to the collaboration (Figure 13). The Collabs section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box, as well as two drop-down menus to filter the results (1).
- Central menu: where you can find all your Collaboration proposals, both the new ones that the user has sent, as well as those that they have received with the current status to take action and progress quickly (2).

You can collaborate by clicking on the "Collaborate" button when you see a person's profile. You can find the members within the top menus (Citizens, Innovation Sector, Policy Makers and Researchers). You can also chat with the person before sending them a collaboration proposal.

Figure 13 Collaboration Section

2.2.12 Network

The Network section (Figure 14) will consist in one zone, the central menu (1): this is a place inside the Dashboard where user can create his/her own list of Professionals (Citizens, Innovation Sector, Policy Makers and Researchers), create a list of people to follow, etc.

You can add Professionals by clicking on the "Add to my Network" button when you look into user's profile.

The list of Citizens, Innovation Sector, Policy Makers and Researchers will appear in the central menu.

Figure 14 Network Section

2.2.13 Radar

This section displays the Opportunities that users have chosen from the Marketplace section. Users can follow these opportunities' progress and remain informed of new developments (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Radar Section

The Radar section will consist in one zone:

- Central menu (1): this is a place inside the Dashboard where user can create his/her own list of Opportunities and save them for later or create a list of best practices to follow or services that user is interested in, or funding opportunities that user want to keep in mind.

You can add Opportunities in this section by clicking on the "Add to my Radar" button when you look an opportunity in the marketplace section.

The list of Opportunities will appear in the central menu.

2.2.14 Opportunities

The Opportunities that users have suggested or chosen to collaborate on are shown in this section (Figure 16). Users can view each opportunity's specifics and follow the development of their collaborations.

Figure 16 Opportunities Marketplace

The Opportunities section will consist in one zone:

- Central menu (1): this is a place inside the Dashboard where user can create his/her own list of Opportunities and save them for later or create a list of opportunities for collaboration, services, fundings or when the user is looking for a partner for a Consortium.

2.2.15 Resources

Users of the AE Virtual Lab have access to useful resources and tools for the study of agroecology through the Resources sections of the lab (Figure 17). Based on collaboration between AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, this part intends to support users in their efforts to advance the subject of agroecology by keeping them informed, involved, and motivated. The resources section may include publications, case studies, data sets, and other tools that users can utilise to support their research or partnerships.

Figure 17 Resource Center

The Resources section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box, as well as two drop-down menus to filter the results. (1)
- Central menu: the search results will present the data of the Resources that fit the search and filtering criteria as a list (2).

2.2.16 News

The News section provides users with the latest news and updates related to agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, such as new AE practices implemented, funding opportunities, workshops and new research findings Figure 18. This section is designed to keep users informed and up-to-date with the latest developments in the field and to provide them with the resources they need to collaborate and innovate effectively.

Figure 18 News Section

The News section will be divided into two zones:

- Top menu: which will consist of a search box. (1)
- Central menu: the search results will present as a list, relevant articles, news and interviews that fit the search and filtering criteria (2), published in the websites of Communities, Ecosystems and other sources own websites.

2.2.17 Data

As data management becomes increasingly important for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, the use of blockchain technology can be an effective way to ensure the security and integrity of data. A function that provides blockchain services as part of a AE Virtual lab can help living labs and research infrastructures manage and share data securely and transparently.

By using blockchain, the platform can ensure that data is stored in a decentralised, tamper-proof manner that is resistant to hacking or manipulation. Additionally, by providing a transparent record of data transactions, blockchain can help increase accountability and trust between different collaborators and stakeholders. Overall, integrating blockchain technology into a networking and collaboration platform for AE living labs and research infrastructures can help ensure the reliability and security of data management, which is crucial for advancing research and innovation in the field.

Different services can be potentially developed and access from the AE Virtual Lab such as:

- Secure and tamper-proof ledger for data storage and sharing.
- Decentralised database of information to increase trust and accountability.
- Gamification of living labs using blockchain to incentivise engagement and participation, such as awarding tokens for completing tasks or achieving goals.
- Facilitation of smart contracts to automate processes and transactions, reducing the need for intermediaries.

- Creation of a secure voting system for decision-making processes.
- Creation of a token economy within the platform, incentivising participation and collaboration.

Figure 19 Data Section

The Data section will consist in one zone:

- Central menu (1): this is a place inside the Dashboard where user can access the Blockchain services "LifeBlock" from LifeWatch ERIC.

2.2.18 Notifications

By clicking on the bell icon in the upper right corner, the user can access to the Notification section.

Figure 20 Notifications Section

In this section the user can modify the notification preferences (1).

2.2.19 Log Out

In this section the user can log out his or her session and leave the portal.

Figure 21 Log out Screen

3. Report on Training 1, November 23rd, 2022, Budapest, Hungary

3.1 Organising Team & Facilitator

LifeWatch ERIC Technical Team: Juan Miguel González Aranda (Chief Technology Officer, CF.ES ICT Core Director), José Manuel Ávila Castuera (Agroecology Coordinator), Antonio José Sáenz Albanés (e-Infrastructure Operation Coordinator), Iria Soto Embodas (Agroecology Project Manager)

Facilitator: José Manuel Ávila Castuera (LifeWatch ERIC)

Co-organisers and Notetakers: Iria Soto Embodas (LifeWatch ERIC)

3.2 Objective of the Training

This workshop aimed to train participants on the pre-operational version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab (AE Virtual Lab) and validate the current version of the platform. This version of the AE Virtual Lab includes testing versions of different functionalities related to collaboration and networking.

Training included various topics starting from a summary of the co-creation activities performed for the development of the AE Lab and the different phases of platform development, an introduction of the current version of the AE Virtual Lab and the Validation Process, a demonstration of the functioning of the tool and the onboarding process. The session was finalised by validating the tool and describing the next steps. The information collected after the workshop will help to improve the functionalities of the tool and deliver the next versions.

The training methodology was interactive as the trainers ensured that knowledge was not only disseminated but accurately perceived and understood by the participants. And in order to provide this, trainers engaged participants in discussions and kept the forum open for feedback, queries and suggestions. These discussions and interactive sessions were supported through PowerPoint presentations, videos and a post-training questionnaire.

3.3 Agenda

14:30 – 14:35	Intro, objectives, method
14:35 – 14:55	Summary of the last meeting: main functionalities
14:55 – 15:30	Presentation: AE Virtual Lab - testing version

15:30 – 16:00	Practical session: the onboarding of the testing group sign-in and log-in
16:00 – 16:20	validation of the first testing version of the AE Virtual Lab
16:20 – 16:30	Next steps and conclusion

The timing was in accordance with the proposed agenda.

3.4 Summary of the Proceedings

The session was organised in the following items:

- Co-design process
- Mockups
- Development & KeyUserGroup
- Onboarding process
- Validation
- Next steps

3.4.1 Summary of the discussion points

The presentation started with a summary of the main steps for the co-design of the Agroecology Virtual Lab developed during the two Workshops organised in the context of the previous Pilot Network meetings (Figure 22).

1. Last meetings summary

4 specific questions were addressed to co-design the Agroecology Virtual Lab

Figure 22 Introduction to the co-design process for defining the characteristics and functionalities of the AE Virtual Lab

3.4.2 Mockups

Introduction of the mockups of the next version of the AE Virtual Lab. During the presentation different sections were presented:

- **Login Page:** the proposed version of the login page was shown.
- **Dashboard:** This page includes tips and guides to use the platform, community events, collaboration status, messaging chat messages, matches and new members.
- **Marketplace:** This section includes search engine optimisation with elastic search technology where public funding, innovation programs, public procurement, and challenges are aggregated. Members can add their research results, services, technology, research projects, challenges, needs, or looking for consortium partners.
- **Profile:** Every profile from every member will find other members with clear information needed to quickly make a decision to connect and collaborate. Collaborations can be made between individual members (Figure 23).
- **Find users:** There are four directories for the space ecosystem: Researchers, Policy makers, Innovation sector, and Citizens. In every Directory, every member will find other members with clear information needed to contact and collaborate.

Figure 23 Mockup for Profile section

3.4.3 Development and Key User Group

The session was followed by a short description of platform development strategies following an agile approach. Agile is an iterative approach to project management and software development that helps developers deliver value to their end-users faster and with solutions more aligned with their needs. Instead of betting everything on a launch at the end of the project, an agile team delivers work in small, but consumable increments. Requirements, plans, and results are evaluated continuously, so teams have a natural mechanism for responding to change quickly.

To validate the incremental versions of the tool, a KeyUserGroup is launched. We are focused on researchers but will try to involve other groups such as policymakers, the innovation sector (including farmers, cooperatives, companies, etc.) and citizens.

LifeWatch ERIC will provide help members of the KeyUserGroup by:

- supporting creating a profile, add opportunities, search,
- helping them familiarise with the platform,
- answering all the technical and process questions,
- supporting at any level during the testing period,
- gathering feedback and answer questions,
- showcasing new functionalities.

3.4.4 Onboarding process

The pre-operational version of the tool was introduced to the Pilot Network Members and followed with a demo to show the KeyUserGroup how the AE Virtual Lab works.

During the training, three journeys were organised to show the different functionalities. Videos supported this training and participants were able to practice by themselves with the help of the facilitators (Figure 24).

Figure 24 Journeys during the demo. Green is used to marking the videos used to support the training

3.4.5 Validation

During the validation stage, the main points for discussion were:

- Most participants generally value the current version of the AE Virtual Lab.
- Areas of interest- Provide given vocabulary to prevent misspellings and facilitate matchmaking.
- Adapt the industry field to Natural Sciences and transdisciplinary fields. Allow for multiple selections. Activities – should be more focused on Agriculture
- What about including other actors not belonging to Research Infrastructures or Living Labs? Which type of access? Example of the Network?

- Innovative ways to self-evaluate inspiring practices based on WP1 questionnaires. WP1-WP6 meetings were organised to explore this option.
- Improve messaging services to inform someone when it is offline.
- Highlight compulsory fields in the profile section or opportunity section.
- Explore blockchain solutions for data management.
- Include the database of capacity-building activities that have been developed in WP5.
- Explore automatic translation tools to take advantage of the EU-added value of the tool. Identify which is the best language to accelerate the transition.

Minor comments

- Separate Denmark RI – there are many together.
- Industry - non-profit management change it by non-profit
- Policy makers as LL or RI stakeholders? Do we need to have a group?
- Change inspirational practices by inspiring practices
- Marketplace - Applies to – make a better description – scope/impact of your offer/inquiry
- Reduce compulsory fields.

After the session, a post-workshop survey was sent to provide future comments about the AE Virtual Lab, including an evaluation questionnaire.

3.4.6 Next steps

New sessions were organised during the following months to showcase new functionalities, validate them and receive feedback from KeyUserGroup members.

After this session, a post-training information package was sent to:

- Share the platform link and invite other members in the community of the Pilot Network Members to participate in the validation process.
- Share the material used during the training.
- Receive feedback about the tool and the training.
- Organise the next meeting (December 2022)

3.5 Questionnaire results

After the training, a survey was shared with the participants. One-third of them completed the survey, and their answers were:

- All the participants rated the workshop well, with most of them classifying as Excellent or Good.
- All of them answered that the expectations were fulfilled.
- Some suggestions were:
 - The training was satisfying as it was a good introduction to using the AE Virtual Lab.

- Well organised.

3.6 Conclusions

Overall, the training contributed to explaining to the users the co-creation activities performed for the development of the AE Lab and the different phases of platform development, an introduction of the current version of the AE Virtual Lab and the Validation Process, a demonstration of the functioning of the tool and the onboarding process.

The Pilot Network members positively valued the main functionalities shown in the session. The inputs will be analysed and incorporated into the new releases of the platform. The answers provided will help improve the tool, and the tool will be completed after interactive validation with the Pilot Network members.

All the participants' comments will be analysed in detail, along with the questionnaire responses shared with the members after the session. Then, this information will deliver the next releases for the next validation stage.

The results of the workshop were quite clear. However, some questions need to be further elaborated:

- Language issue.
- How to open the AE Virtual Lab to others than Living Labs and Research Infrastructures.
- How to include the questionnaire for inspiring practices.

To conclude, the objective of the workshop was successfully achieved. After the session, a better understanding of the reasons and characteristics of the tools was obtained, and areas of improvement will be taken into consideration. This information is key to designing tools based on users' needs.

4. Report on Training 2, March 17th, 2023, Online

4.1 Organising Team & Facilitator

LifeWatch ERIC Technical Team: Juan Miguel González Aranda (Chief Technology Officer, CF.ES ICT Core Director), José Manuel Ávila Castuera (Agroecology Coordinator), Antonio José Sáenz Albanés (e-Infrastructure Operation Coordinator), Iria Soto Embodas (Agroecology Project Manager)

Facilitator: José Manuel Ávila Castuera (LifeWatch ERIC)

Co-organisers and Notetakers: Iria Soto Embodas (LifeWatch ERIC)

4.2 Objective of the Training

The objectives of this workshop were to provide attendees with the necessary skills and knowledge to use the Agroecology (AE) Virtual Lab. The workshop aimed to teach attendees all the different functions of the platform related to collaboration, networking and knowledge sharing, but also obtain feedback and inputs from the end-users to improve the tool. During the training, the attendees learnt and tested how to register, log in, create an individual and ecosystem profile, navigate the marketplace, match with others, use the messaging system, and upload and access news and resources. A specific time for open discussions allowed attendees to ask questions, share their experiences, and provide feedback.

After a short introduction about the AE Virtual Lab, the training was divided into two parts, with an open discussion after each part. The first part of the session focused on introducing the platform being used, covering topics such as registration and login, profile creation, marketplace and the description of matchmaking functions. The second part covered topics about how to create a profile of a Living Labs or Research Infrastructure, messages and resources and news. The session finished with a wrap-up and conclusion, where the key takeaways were summarised.

The trainers used an interactive training methodology to make sure that the information was not only shared but also correctly perceived and understood by the participants. Instructors encouraged conversation among the attendees and left time for questions, comments, and suggestions. These discussions and interactive sessions were supported through a short PowerPoint presentation, a hands-on session and a post-training questionnaire.

4.3 Agenda

10:00h	Welcoming of attendees and short introduction.
10:10h	Training session, 1st part: Register/Login, Profile, Marketplace, Match
10:40h	Open discussion
11:00h	Short Break
11:10h	Training session, 2nd part. Ecosystem, Messages, Resources.
11:40h	Open discussion
11:50h	Wrap up and Conclusion

12:00h End of Session

The timing was in accordance with the proposed agenda.

4.4 Summary of the Proceedings

The session started with a short presentation that explained the new functionalities of the platform and the co-design and development process. Then, the training was organised as a hands-on session in which, the main elements of the platform were tested. The session was organised in the following items corresponding to the platform's different sections:

- Registration and Login
- Profile
- The Marketplace
- The Dashboard
- The Ecosystem profile
- Messaging
- Resources & News

The session finalised with the final remarks and conclusions.

4.4.1 Registration and Login

The session began with a registration process where participants were asked to create a profile (Figure 25). The trainer asked a participant to share their screen and complete the required fields. Next, the trainer demonstrated how to view the profile, explore different user types, and use the search function. Participants were also shown how to add contacts to their Network.

During the session, trainers helped participants to understand the different fields and identify their own keywords and main interests in order to optimise the collaboration with other users.

After completing the profiles, trainees learnt how to search for other users and include them in their Network. This makes it easier to collaborate on projects in the future.

Figure 25 Edit Profile screen of a user during the hands-on session

4.4.2 Marketplace

A marketplace of the AE Virtual Lab is a section of the platform where users can discover and post collaboration opportunities in agroecology (Figure 26). This section is designed to facilitate the exchange of expertise, knowledge and resources between users of AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures and foster collaboration and innovation in the field.

The marketplace would allow users to post opportunities for collaboration, such as research projects, workshops, and training programs. It would provide a centralised location for users to discover and connect with others who share similar interests and skills. The marketplace would use a collaboration canvas, which is a tool to help users describe their project, specify the roles they are looking to fill, and outline the resources required.

Figure 26 Screen with the section Marketplace during the training session

The platform would also include a search function that allows users to search for opportunities based on keywords, location, or other criteria. Users can also view opportunities posted by other users, select opportunities they are interested in and send a referral by email to refer other users who they believe would be a good fit for the opportunity.

During the session, the attendees learnt the following functions of the marketplace:

Figure 27 Screen during the session to create an opportunity in the marketplace

- **Create an Opportunity:** Trainees created an opportunity for collaboration by completing the required fields. In these fields, the users describe their project, specify the roles they are looking to fill, and outline the resources required (Figure 27).
- **View the Opportunity:** Once an opportunity is posted, it can be viewed by other users. The opportunity will include details such as the project description, required skills, and location.
- **Search for Opportunities:** Users learnt how to search for opportunities based on keywords, location, or other criteria. The platform displays a list of opportunities that match the user's search criteria.
- **Select an Opportunity:** Users can select an opportunity they are interested in and send a referral by email. This allows users to refer other users they believe would be a good fit for the opportunity. But also trainees learnt how to ask for collaboration based on the opportunities selected in the marketplace.

4.4.3 Dashboard

The dashboard section of the AE Virtual Lab is a homepage that displays important information and tools for users. In this context, the Dashboard was designed to provide an overview of important information and tools related to events, news, tips, ongoing collaborations, new platform members and new marketplace opportunities, and new resources. Furthermore, from the Dashboard, users can access to specific menus with different sections to promote collaboration.

During the session, participants were introduced to the Dashboard and the different sections of the Menu that can help use the platform and foster collaboration (Figure 28). The participants practised, tested and learnt the following functions: explained how opportunities proposed in the marketplace would appear in the Opportunities section. The Matches section would suggest opportunities and users based on the own keywords and descriptions. The Radar section would show the opportunities selected in the marketplace, while the Collabs section would display opportunities where participants had chosen to collaborate.

Figure 28 Dashboard of a participant during the training session

Here are some of the key features of the dashboard section:

- **Opportunities:** This section displays the opportunities that users have proposed or selected to collaborate on. Users can view the details of each opportunity and track the progress of their collaborations.
- **Radar:** This section displays the opportunities that users have selected from the marketplace section. Users can track the progress of these opportunities and stay up-to-date with the latest developments.
- **Collabs:** This section displays ongoing collaborations that users are involved in. Users can view the progress of their collaborations, communicate with other collaborators, and access important documents and resources related to the collaboration.
- **Matches:** This section displays potential collaborations based on keywords and descriptions that match the user's profile and interests. Users can review the matches and reach out to other users to initiate new collaborations.

4.4.4 Ecosystem

Participants were asked to complete the different fields for the Ecosystem feature (Figure 29). This section includes a template in which the Coordinator of the Living Lab or Research Infrastructure can provide information about the organisation. Moreover, the Ecosystem will appear in the section Map once the address is included.

Figure 29 Screen with the Ecosystem Search page

During the session, the Coordinator of the Living Lab or Research Infrastructure were able to edit the information (Figure 30). Moreover, they explored how to search the Ecosystem in the platform.

Figure 30 Screen for editing the information of the Ecosystem

4.4.5 Messages

The Messages section is where users can communicate with each other using different messaging tools (Figure 31). The trainer demonstrated how to use direct messages, attach files by dragging and dropping, create a channel, and create a team.

Figure 31 Screen with the Messages section during the training session

Participants were shown how to interact with the following functions:

- Direct Messages: This is the most common type of messaging. Users can send direct messages to each other, much like a traditional chat application. Direct Messages are private and only visible to the users involved in the conversation.
- Attach Files: Users can attach files to their messages by simply dragging and dropping them into the chat window.
- Create a Channel: Users can create a channel for group conversations. Channels can be public or private, and users can invite other users to join the channel (Figure 32).
- Create a Team: Teams are groups of users who work together on a project. Users can create teams, add members, and communicate with each other using the team messaging tool.
- Room Information: Users can view information about the room, including the name of the room, the members in the room, and the messages sent in the room.
- See Members: Users can view the members of a room, copy links to the room, and add members to a Living Lab.
- Search Messages/Files: Users can search for specific messages or files by entering a keyword or phrase.
- Notification Preferences: Users can customise their notification preferences for different types of messages and activities.
- Starred Messages: Users can mark important messages as "starred" for easy reference later.

- Off-the-Record Option: Users can enable an "off-the-record" option to ensure that their messages are not saved in the system's logs.

Figure 32 Screen of a Channel in the Messaging

4.4.6 Resources sections

The Resources sections of the AE Virtual Lab provide users with access to valuable information and tools related to the field of agroecology. This section aims to help users stay informed, engaged, and inspired as they work to advance the field of agroecology based on collaboration between AE Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. The resources section may include a variety of resources such as publications, case studies, data sets, and other tools that users can use to support their research or collaborations.

Participants were asked to prepare resources from a file and they attached to their own Ecosystem (Figure 33).

Figure 33 Screen during the session where a participant added a Resource

4.4.7 News and Event sections

The News and Events section provides users with the latest updates on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, such as upcoming events, funding opportunities, workshops and new research findings. Both sections are designed to keep users informed and up-to-date with the latest developments in the field and provide them with the resources they need to collaborate and innovate effectively. During the session, the participants were able to add a new event to the AE Virtual Lab (Figure 34).

Figure 34 Screen during the session where a participant added a new event

4.4.8 Wrap up and Conclusions

The session ended with a discussion on onboarding and the operational version of the platform.

In general, the participants agreed on the central answers to the questions. There were no diverging points or strong disagreements.

- Better selection of Research Sector Vocabulary
- Add password recovery
- Provide different websites
- Discussion about how to register new ecosystems
- Coming events, dates should be changed.

Participants were encouraged to disseminate the platform through their Network and provide feedback after a month of use to help improve the platform's features and usability.

Overall, the training session provided participants with a comprehensive introduction to a collaboration platform's features, including profile creation, the marketplace, the Dashboard, the Ecosystem, messages, resources, and news. Participants were encouraged to use the platform actively and provide feedback to help improve it. After this session, a survey was sent to evaluate the training.

4.5 Questionnaire results

After the training, a survey was shared with the participants. Half of them completed the survey and their answers were:

- All the participants rated the workshop well, with most of them classifying as Excellent or Good.
- However, for half of the participants, the expectations were only partially fulfilled.
- Some suggestions were:
 - Take more time for stimulating the participants to try the different functions.
 - In presence workshop would be preferable.

4.6 Conclusions

The training session gave participants a thorough introduction to all of the aspects of a collaboration platform, including the establishment of profiles, the marketplace, the Dashboard, the Ecosystem, messages, resources, and news. Participants were urged to actively use the site, disseminate the platform through their Network and offer suggestions for improvements.

5. Conclusions

Virtual Research Environments (VRE) can provide seamless access to data, software, and processing resources from different domains through a secure and collaborative web platform. The Agroecology Virtual Lab, co-designed and developed in ALL-Ready, is a collaborative platform for members of Living Labs, Research Infrastructures and other Open Innovation Arrangements to connect and share knowledge in the field of agroecology, promoting sustainable and equitable food systems. The platform provides various functionalities, such as the visualisation of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures maps, best practices, networking tools, and knowledge-sharing repositories. The platform's design is based on a participatory approach involving a KeyUserGroup, representatives of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, and workshops, training, and questionnaires to identify and prioritise the functionalities.

During the second part of the project, the AE Virtual Lab was upgraded based on a collaborative process that includes careful planning and implementation, teamwork, and a focus on meeting user needs and requirements. The development process involved a KeyUserGroup that validated the incremental versions of the tool and provided feedback on its features and changes. LifeWatch ERIC provided help to the KeyUserGroup in creating profiles, searching, and understanding the platform. The development process followed an agile methodology, which included designing and validating the new features and changes, coding and implementing them, extensively testing the new releases, and monitoring and updating them based on user feedback.

This document introduced the upgraded version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab. The platform offers users a range of tools, resources, and information related to sustainable agriculture and rural development, as well as features that enable collaboration, networking, and access to relevant news, events, and opportunities. It includes the different features and functionalities of the platform, such as the login page, dashboard, profile, marketplace, messages, citizen, innovation sector, policy makers, researchers, ecosystems, maps, graphs, matches, collabs, network, radar, opportunities, resources, news, data, notifications, and log out.

Two workshops were organised for the presentation, validation and training in the use of the AE Virtual Lab. These two training workshops contributed to train participants, but also obtain feedback from end-users to improve the tool. The first training (November 2022) aimed to instruct participants on the pre-operational version of the AE Virtual Lab and validate mockups and preliminary functionalities of the platform. The second training (March 2023) aimed to provide attendees with the necessary skills and knowledge to use the AE Virtual Lab. The workshop aimed to teach attendees all the different functions of the platform related to collaboration, networking and knowledge sharing.

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